

Effect of carbofuran application on leaffolder incidence, Aduthurai, India, 1982-83.

Treatment	Leaffolder damage (%)
Control	27.1
0.5 kg carbofuran ai/ha incorporated at planting	24.5
0.5 kg carbofuran ai/ha topdressed at 15 DT	21.1
0.75 kg carbofuran ai/ha incorporated at planting	26.4
0.75 kg carbofuran ai/ha topdressed at 15 DT	19.7
1.0 kg carbofuran ai/ha topdressed at 15 DT	17.6
CD	NS

to subplots in 3 splits – 50% basal, 25% at active tillering, and 25% at panicle initiation. Leaffolder incidence on 10 hills/plot was recorded at 60 DT by counting the total and damaged leaves and calculating the percentage.

Method of carbofuran application did not significantly influence leaffolder incidence. However, topdressing of carbo-

Effect of nitrogen level on leaffolder incidence.

furan at 15 DT caused a slight decrease in the pest incidence (see table). Increased levels of nitrogen application caused a

corresponding increase in pest population (see figure). Carbofuran-nitrogen interaction was not significant. □

A new predaceous beetle of whitebacked planthopper in India

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Whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) *Sogatella furcifera* (Horvath) is a potentially destructive rice pest during kharif in Madhya Pradesh. Populations are suppressed by several enemies including mirid bug *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis*. Staphylinid beetle *Paederus fuscipes* Curtis (Staphylinidae: Coleoptera) is a predator of brown planthopper (BPH) in Malaysia, Japan, Taiwan, and Thailand. Two species of this beetle, *P. fuscipes* and *P. melampus* Er., feed on BPH in India.

Large populations (25-30 beetles/hill) of staphylinid beetle *P. fuscipes* were found in fields in Apr 1981, feeding on WBPH nymphs. In confinement the beetles also preferred nymphs. This is the first record of *P. fuscipes* in M. P., India. □

Attraction of rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* to light sources

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Gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason) is a major rice pest in India and in Tamil Nadu State. Infestations occur from Aug to Feb with maximum populations between Sep and Nov. Gall midge attraction to different light sources and light traps

was studied at the Agricultural College and Research Institute, Madurai. A bamboo trap with a 40W incandescent bulb, a bamboo trap with a 250W infrared lamp, and a Robinson type trap with a 125W mercury vapor lamp were set up in a triangle over the field. The trap positions were randomly interchanged each day after morning counts. Total weekly gall midge catches were combined over 4 weeks and compared.

The bamboo trap with 250W infrared light source attracted the most insects, followed by the 40W incandescent light

Attraction of rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* to different light sources, Madurai, India, 1981.

Week ending	40W incandescent lamp	250W infrared lamp	125W HPL mercury vapor lamp
19 Sep 81	149 (2.17)	360 (2.56)	69 (1.84)
26 Sep 81	120 (2.08)	258 (2.41)	35 (1.54)
3 Oct 81	140 (2.15)	274 (2.44)	67 (1.83)
10 Oct 81	155 (2.19)	255 (2.41)	52 (1.72)
Total	(8.59)	(9.82)	(6.93)
Mean	(2.15)	(2.46)	(1.73)

^a Figures in parentheses are transformed values.

trap and the Robinson trap (see table). The Robinson trap may have trapped fewer midges because the high-intensity

light attracted many kinds of insects, including large ones, which made it difficult for fragile, smaller gall midges to reach

the trap. It also may be that the photokinetic response of gall midge is greater toward the infrared range. □

Brown planthopper biotypes in Korea

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Brown planthopper (BPH) populations come to Korea on prevailing low-pressure winds from southern China during the crop growing season. We studied the distribution of migrating BPH biotypes in Korea. Seventy-eight BPH females were collected from the southwest coast of the Korean peninsula 23-27 Aug 1982. They

were individually reared for two to three generations on susceptible rice variety Milyang 23 in the greenhouse.

Differential varieties were Milyang 23 with no resistance gene, Cheongcheongbyeon with *Bph 1* resistance gene, and Milyang 63 with *bph 2* resistance gene (see table).

BPH biotypes from each local collection were differentiated using the seedling bulk testing method. Results showed 61 local collections were BPH biotype 1, 8 were biotype 2, and 9 were biotype 3 (see figure). □

Reaction of different rice varieties to BPH biotypes and local collections in Korea in 1982.

Variety	Resistance gene	Damage rating ^a					
		Biotype			Local collections from		
		1	2	3	Ashan	Hongseong	Boseong
Milyang 23	None	S	S	S	S	S	S
Cheongcheongbyeon	<i>Bph 1</i>	R	S	R	R	S	R
Milyang 63	<i>bph 2</i>	R	R	S	R	R	S

Based on seedling bulk test. R = resistant, S = susceptible.

Distribution of brown planthopper biotypes in Korea.

A simple technique for rearing rice thrips in the glasshouse

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Identification of varietal resistance to rice thrips *Stenchaetothrips (Baliothrips) biformis* (Bagnell) requires a mass screening technique that can be used in the glasshouse. We tested techniques for mass rearing rice thrips.

Rice seedlings heavily infested with thrips were uprooted from the field and planted in groups of 5 in shallow 15- × 27- × 6-cm plastic planting flats in the glasshouse. Each group of infested seedlings was surrounded by 4 groups of 1-week-old Bg 34-8 uninfested seedlings. Distance between seedling groups was 3-5 cm.

Thrips moved from the infested seedlings to the uninfested ones and reproduced. The colony was maintained by uprooting newly infested seedlings and planting new seedlings. A colony was successfully maintained for more than 4 months (about 6 generations) and each flat of infested seedlings could be used to infest 3 to 5 trays of uninfested seedlings. It took about 30 minutes to plant one flat of seedlings. □

Neem (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss) products for control of rice stem borers

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The insect antifeedant properties of neem (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss) oil seed are well known. In addition to phagodeterrence, insect growth-disrupting properties have also been attributed to several neem derivatives. Cake made from neem seeds after oil extraction has been reported to be an excellent insect repellent, organic